

An Introduction to Electrospray Ionization and Matrix Assisted Laser Desorption/Ionization Mass Spectrometry : Essential Tools in the Modern Drug Discovery Process†

ASHIT K. GANGULY* and BIRENDRA N. PRAMANIK

Schering-Plough Research Institute, 2015 Galloping Hill Road, Kenilworth, New Jersey 07033, U.S.A.

Manuscript received 30 July 1998

The process of discovering and developing new biologically active pharmaceutical compounds from synthetic and natural sources is very complex and highly competitive. The rapid and accurate structural characterization of the drug candidate when bound to the disease causing protein is essential to this discovery process, and in this paper we would like to demonstrate the use of mass spectrometry (MS) to achieve this goal.

The compounds of interest range from small molecules with molecular weights of a few hundred Daltons to proteins of mass greater than 100 kDa. Analysis of small molecules is usually carried out by the traditional ionization methods of Electron Impact (EI), Chemical Ionization (CI) and Fast Atom Bombardment (FAB). The late eighties and early nineties have seen the introduction and development of two new MS ionization techniques, electrospray ionization (ESI)¹ and matrix assisted laser desorption/ionization (MALDI)², that has produced a remarkable extension of the MS analytical mass range, even up to 500 kDa³. Another important feature of these MS methods is the small quantities of material required for the analysis.

At Schering, in an effort to provide full MS support for the drug discovery process, a complete mass spectrometry facility with the latest technologies was established and has been continually upgraded. In this report, we will examine our use of ESI and MALDI, with their greatly enhanced mass range and facile ionization capability for large polar molecules, to solve difficult biomedical structural problems. To illustrate these new capabilities, the following examples will be discussed with brief introduction of the techniques : (1) the determination of the molecular weight, with ESI, of α -2b interferon (IFN; SCH 30500) and of CHO interleukin-4 (IL-4), (2) the use of enzymatic cleavage (trypsin) in conjunction with ESI to provide sequence mapping of α -2b interferon, (3) the use of MALDI for intractable protein problems such as glycoproteins and (4) the study of human *ras* oncoprotein-GDP, and *ras*-inhibitors noncovalent complexes utilizing ESI.

Analysis of recombinant proteins by ESI and MALDI MS

Molecular weight determination of proteins produced by recombinant DNA techniques is an important first step in their quality control and structure characterization. The recently developed techniques of ESI and MALDI have en-

abled the analysis of proteins with molecular weights up to 500 kDa for low femtomole quantities.

Electrospray is a newly developed MS ionization technique^{1,4,5} that allows large, polar molecules to be ionized directly from solution at atmospheric pressure. The ionization process takes place during the electrostatic and pneumatic nebulization of a solution of charged analyte ions to form liquid droplets at atmospheric pressure. Convective heat exchange and interaction with air causes rapid size reduction of the droplet to a point where the repulsive coulombic forces approach the level of the droplet's cohesive forces. When this *Rayleigh limit* is reached, the large droplets appear to 'explode' to produce a cascade of fission products comprising smaller and smaller droplets. The repulsive forces within these tiny droplets appear to cause an induced 'ion evaporation' of the dissolved analyte ion which effectively transfers the ion from the condensed phase to the gas phase. These gas phase ions are subsequently focused and transmitted into the mass filter for mass analysis. Fig. 1 illustrates this ESI process.

When an aqueous solution of a protein is sprayed from a fine ESI needle held at high potential, 3–5 kV, multiply charged ions are formed. Due to the multiple charge on these ions, the mass-to-charge (m/z) ratio, which is what the mass spectrometer actually measures, is reduced. Thus, these ions

Fig. 1. Schematic of ion formation in the ESI process.

†Dedicated to Professor Sukh Dev on the occasion of his 75th birthday.

Fig. 2A. Molecular weight determination from multiple charge ion profile by electrospray mass spectrometry.

Fig. 2B. Deconvolution scheme for molecular weight calculation from raw spectral data.

can easily be measured by a typical quadrupole system with a mass range of 3000 Da and a mass accuracy exceeding 0.01%. These ions are observed as an envelope of peaks resulting from the variation in the m/z value produced by differing multiple charge states caused by a varying degree of protonation. The molecular weight of the protein can be derived from the masses of two ions of successive multiple charge states by the formula shown in Fig. 2a; an example of a typical calculation is illustrated in Fig. 2b. These calculations are now readily computed with special deconvolution algorithm programs that are supplied by the mass spectrometry manufacturing companies.

Fig. 3 depicts the ESI mass spectrum of interferon (IFN) α -2b (SCH 30500), an antiviral/anticancer agent marketed worldwide by Schering-Plough. The multiply charge ions yielded the deconvoluted spectrum shown in the inset of

Fig. 3. ESI mass spectrum of rhIFN α -2b; the measured M value is 19266.3 as shown in the deconvoluted spectrum (inset).

Fig. 3 which has the average molecular weight (MW) value of 19266 Da. This value is within good agreement with the calculated average value for IFN α -2b of 19265.4 Da. The high accuracy of the ESI method, which is usually within 1–2 Da for proteins up to 30 kDa, assured the integrity of this protein product including the presence of two disulfide bridges. The presence of the disulfide bridges was confirmed by peptide mapping. The above mass accuracy is substantially better than the results obtained by the more commonly used chemical methods of gel-permeation chromatography and SDS-gel electrophoresis.

Additional structural information can be derived from controlled chemical or enzymatic degradation of the protein into smaller peptide fragments followed by direct probe MS⁶ and/or LC-ESI MS analysis of the resulting peptide mixture. This method of obtaining structural information of a protein is known as peptide mapping. Fig. 4 displays the total ion current chromatogram (TIC) of tryptic peptides generated from a trypsin digest of IFN α -2b; trypsin cleaves the protein at arginine and lysine residues. The IFN α -2b molecule contains four cysteines (Cys) at positions 1, 29, 98 and 138; these residues are responsible for the disulfide linkages. After a complete tryptic digest, these cysteine residues are present in the tryptic peptides T₁, T₅, T₁₀ and T₁₇ respectively. The mapping results obtained from the data presented in Fig. 4 established that Cys(1) was linked to Cys(98) and Cys(29) to Cys(138) via disulfide bonds which corresponded to T₁-S-S-T₁₀ at 4616 Da (Fig. 4A) and T₅-S-S-T₁₇ at 2118 Da (Fig. 4B) respectively. This assignment agreed with previously reported results acquired by HPLC; since MS provides molecular weight evidence to directly support the assignment of the location of the disulfide bonds, it is superior to the HPLC method.

Post-translational modifications of the protein, such as

Fig. 4. Total ion current (TIC) chromatogram from LC-ESI MS analysis of the IFN α -2b tryptic digest (* denotes disulfide linked peptides).

Fig. 4A. ESI mas spectrum of peak T₁-T₁₀ in Fig. 4; the measured value is 4616.3 as shown in the deconvoluted spectrum (inset).

Fig. 4B. ESI mas spectrum of peak T₅-T₁₇ in Fig. 4; the measured value is shown in the deconvoluted spectrum (inset).

oxidation, phosphorylation, sulfation, can be readily detected from the shift of the observed molecular weight. One of the most common modifications is the glycosylation of the protein; Fig. 5 shows the MW determination of the CHO cell-derived interleukin-4 (IL-4) that has been modified by glycosylation. This spectrum provides us with an excellent preliminary view of the number of different glycoforms present in the mammalian cell-derived protein, and it can be used as a first step for heterogeneity checking of the manufacturing batches prior to extensive MS mapping⁷.

MALDI is an alternative MS ionization method used for the analysis of large and complex biomolecules. In this technique, the biomolecule is mixed with a UV- or IR-absorbing matrix which is present at large excess (5000 : 1) and the resulting solution is deposited on a sample target, dried and then inserted into the mass spectrometer.

The matrix performs two important functions : (i) to iso-

late and protect the analyte molecules from direct intense exposure to laser irradiation that would cause extensive fragmentation and (ii) to absorb the photons from the UV laser. Large biomolecules are readily vaporized as part of the matrix plume and are ionized by charge exchange reactions; singly charged ions are the most abundant species in the spectrum, but doubly, triply and quadruply charged ions are also present. The MALDI technique is an extremely sensitive method for the analysis of higher MW biomolecules (500 kDa) from low-femtomole amounts of material; the sensitivity achieved with MALDI is more than 10 times that of ESI.

Fig. 6 displays the MALDI results obtained with 2 μ mol of IFN α -2b. These results can be compared to the results shown in Fig. 3 for ESI (50 μ mol by direct infusion or 200 μ mol by LC-ESI MS), to demonstrate the greater sensitivity of MALDI. MALDI MS is especially useful in the analy-

Fig. 5. ESI deconvoluted mass spectrum of CHO IL-4 showing different glycoforms of the protein.

Fig. 6 MALDI mass spectrum of IFN α -2b using sinapinic acid as a matrix and H_2O /acetonitrile with 0.1% TFA as the solvent.

Fig. 7 MALDI mass spectrum of immunoglobulin G using sinapinic acid as a matrix and H_2O /acetonitrile with 0.1% TFA as the solvent

sis of higher molecular weight glycoproteins (e.g. IL-5, IL-4R, IL-5R) where the ESI method has not been successful⁸. Glycoproteins with molecular weights in the range of 20000 Da or less, such as CHO IL-4, can be analyzed by both techniques. However, the experience of this laboratory and others⁸ indicate that glycoproteins with molecular weights of 30000 Da or greater can only be analyzed by MALDI. Fig. 7 is the MALDI spectrum of 10 μ mol of IgG, the principal antibody protein in serum. An average molecular weight of 148610 Da was calculated from the results in Fig. 7 with a 0.1% accuracy; this value was obtained by averaging the four charge states present in the spectrum (singly charged at 148610 Da, doubly at 74308 Da, triply at 49531 Da and quadruply at 37146 Da). The poor mass accuracy (0.1%) found in MALDI at higher masses is characteristic of time of flight analyzers used in commercial laser instruments. Finally, MALDI has been found to be more versatile for the analysis of complex mixtures of biomolecules. This is because of the greater simplicity of its spectrum compared to ESI (without LC); MALDI has fewer charge states.

Analysis of *Ras* Noncovalent Complexes by ESI MS

In recent years, the ESI technique has been used with a considerable success towards the detection of noncovalent complexes under physiological condition⁹. In our laboratory, we have developed an ESI-based methodology for the study of the complexing of guanosine diphosphate (GDP) to genetically-engineered version of the human *ras* protein¹⁰, the *ras* protein sequence is shown in Fig. 8. *Ras* proteins are regulatory guanine nucleotide binding proteins, which only in the GTP-bound active form, serve as signal transducers controlling cell proliferation or differentiation. Malignancies in many different tissue types are in part brought on by mutations in the *ras* oncogene, which 'locks' the *ras* in the active state resulting in unregulated cell growth. The power of this ESI approach for the study of noncovalent interactions was further tested by the successful detection

```

1  MTEYK LVVVG AGGVG KSALT IQLIQ NHFVD
31 EYDPT IEDSY RKQVV IDGET CLLDI LDTAG
61 QEEYS AMRDQ YMRTG EGFLC VFAIN NTKSF
91 EDIHQ YREQI KRVKD SDDVP MVLVG NKCDL
121 AARTV ESRQA QDLAR SYGIP YIETS AKTRQ
151 GVEDA FYTLV REIRQ H

```

Fig. 8. Primary structure of human H-*ras* (1-166) protein (calculated isotopically averaged molecular weight 18853.3)

of a γ -interferon dimer¹¹ (MW 33819 Da); this is an example of protein-protein noncovalent interaction with a weaker binding constant.

Our drug discovery efforts involve the development of new compounds that bind noncovalently to disease causing proteins to block the disease mechanism. Thus, our strategy is to identify biologically active compounds that would bind to the *ras* protein at a site other than the nucleotide binding site and inactivate *ras* by preventing the exchange of GTP for GDP. Since our initial involvement with this project in 1990, we have developed an ESI MS based methodologies^{10,12} for the detection of the noncovalently associated *ras* : GDP, *ras* : GTP, and the ternary complexes of *ras* : GDP with organic inhibitors^{13,14}. ESI MS analysis of the noncovalent *ras* : GDP and *ras* : GTP complexes gave multiply-charged ion envelopes corresponding to the *ras* : GDP and *ras* : GTP complexes, with an average molecular mass of 19295 and 19374 Da respectively. Key to the successful detection of these noncovalent complexes, as well as the stability of the observed signals, was the solvent system employed in the sample preparation and the ESI MS analysis. Both the pH and the organic content of the solvent sys-

Fig. 9. Deconvoluted ESI mass spectra of *ras*-GDP complex obtained from protein solution with (A) water-2 mM NH_4OAc , pH 5.8, (B) methanol : water (1 : 1) 5% acetic acid, pH 2.7; (C) methanol : water (1 : 9) 2 mM NH_4OAc , pH 5.8

Fig. 10. ESI mass spectrum of *ras*-GDP complex at pH 5.8 (1 : 9 methanol : water containing 2 mM NH_4OAc).

tem affected the stability of the noncovalent complexes, as shown in the reconstructed ESI mass spectra of Fig. 9A. The effect of methanol and acetic acid (pH = 2.7) is shown by the complete denaturation of the *ras* : GDP complex (Fig. 9B), whereas addition of 10% methanol into the 2 mM ammonium acetate solution resulted in a partial denaturation of the protein-ligand complex (Fig. 9C). The latter is better illustrated in the ESI spectrum in Fig. 10, where the ion envelopes from the partially denatured complex and the released *ras* protein can be clearly seen.

Because of our considerable success in the use of ESI for the analysis of noncovalent complexes, we have applied this methodology to screening of potential inhibitors of *ras* proteins^{13,14}. The ESI MS of a solution containing *ras* : GDP and Sch 54341 (MW 275) produced a weak signal with a average molecular weight of 19570 Da (Fig. 11A) that represented a ternary noncovalent complex with a 1 : 1 stoichiometry for *ras* : GDP : Sch 54341. It was decided that signal enhancement for these weakly bound complexes was necessary in order to extend the use of ESI method for the analysis of more challenging noncovalent complexes. Therefore, the experimental protocol was refined by reducing the stress on the binding forces of these complexes by altering the following parameters : the infusion flow rate was reduced to 3 $\mu\text{l min}^{-1}$ from 10 $\mu\text{l min}^{-1}$, the orifice voltage was lowered from 80 to 30 V and the nebulizing gas pressure was also reduced. With these modifications to the methodology, the signal for the above ternary complex was enhanced by a factor of 3 (Fig. 11B), Sch 54341 was found to be active *in vitro* assays. This modified ESI method was further tested by studying the results of a well-established noncovalent complex system, FKBP-demethoxy rapamycin (Figs. 12A and 12B). When our results for this complex were compared to a similar FKBP-rapamycin complex reported by Ganem *et al.*⁹, the molecular ion intensity

Fig. 11. Deconvoluted ESI mass spectra of *ras*-GDP and Sch 54341 : (A) before refinement of experimental protocol and (B) after refinement.

Fig. 12. Deconvoluted ESI mass spectra of FKBP-demethoxyrapamycin : (A) before refinement and (B) after refinement.

was increased by approximately an order of magnitude. This dramatic improvement in the detection of the molecular ion intensity of the weakly bound noncovalent complexes has extended the dynamic range of this technique.

Experimental

Electrospray mass spectrometry : A Perkin-Elmer Sciex API III and a API 365 triple quadrupole mass spectrometer equipped with standard atmospheric pressure ionization source were used. The analysis was carried out by scanning the first or third quadrupole from 300 to 2400/3000 Da at a typical scan rate of 2 s/scan. Sample solutions were introduced by either direct infusion of the protein solution or via a Rheodyne external loop injector with a preselected solvent system. In the later case, an Applied Biosystem Inc. Model 140A dual-syringe micro LC pump was used to deliver a constant liquid flow rate in the range of 3–100 $\mu\text{l min}^{-1}$.

On-line microbore LC/MS : The liquid chromatography (LC) system consisted of an ABI Model 140B dual-syringe pump or more recently a Shimadzu pump. A Rheodyne Model biocompatible injector was used for sample introduction onto to a microbore column. An LC-308 microbore column (1 mm i.d. \times 10 cm) or a C18 column (Supelcosil LC-18DB, 1 mm i.d. \times 30 cm) in the case of IFN α -2b tryptic digest was used. Well-resolved chromatographic peaks of tryptic peptides were obtained using a 0.1% trifluoroacetic acid-water-acetonitrile solvent system. A typical run was with a 120 min 0–60% acetonitrile gradient. The entire eluent was introduced into mass spectrometer via an articulated ion-spray interface at a flow rate of 40 μ l min⁻¹. The PE Sciex equipment were operated at unit-mass resolution with a scan rate 3 s/scan over a mass range of 400–3000 Da.

MALDI MS : The MALDI experiments were performed on a PerSeptive Biosystems Voyager-DE STAR biospectrometry workstation equipped with a N₂ laser (337 nm). The linear time of flight (TOF) mode was used for all experiments discussed. The spectrometer was operated at a total accelerating voltage of 25 kV, but due to the two-stage configuration of ion-source, only 90–92% of the total accelerating voltage was actually applied to the ions. Delay times were dependent on the mass of the molecule being analyzed and ranged from 100–1700 ns. In these experiments, sinapinic acid (Aldrich) was used without purification as the matrix. For the laser analysis of IFN α -2b, 1 μ l of sample (1 mg ml⁻¹ aqueous solution buffered with 20 mM of sodium phosphate) was mixed with 4 μ l of matrix before applied to the sample plate and blown-dried. For the IgG experiment, 1 μ l of sample (1.5 mg ml⁻¹ of 0.1% TFA aqueous solution) was mixed with 2 μ l of a matrix solution (50% acetonitrile/aqueous solution containing 0.1% TFA and saturated with sinapinic acid).

Conclusion : Overall, MS methodologies based on ESI and MALDI analysis of higher mass proteins and glycoproteins, have played an important role in the structural characterization of compounds that have been developed as therapeutic agents. In addition, ESI based method for the study of noncovalent complexes, pioneered in our laboratory and few others, has become a major tool in the pharmaceutical industry for screening of potential inhibitors of enzymes and substrates.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank Dr. Yan Hui Liu for technical assistance and Mr. Peter Bartner for help with the manuscript.

References

1. J. B. FENN, M. MANN, C. K. MENG, S. F. WONG and C. M. WHITEHOUSE, *Science*, 1989, **64**, 246; *Mass Spectrom. Rev.*, 1990, **9**, 37.
2. M. KARAS and F. HILLENKAMP, *Anal. Chem.*, 1988, **60**, 2299.
3. F. HILLENKAMP, M. KARAS and S. BERKENKAMP, 'Proceedings of the 43rd ASMS Conference of Mass Spectrometry and Allied Topics', Atlanta, Ga., 1995, p. 357.
4. A. P. BRIUNS, T. R. COVEY and J. D. HENION, *Anal. Chem.*, 1987, **59**, 2642.
5. A. A. THOMSON and J. V. IRIBARNE, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1979, **71**, 4451.
6. B. N. PRAMANIK, A. TSARBOPOULOS, J. E. LABDON, P. P. TROTTA and T. L. NAGABHUSHAN, *J. Chromatogr.*, 1991, **562**, 377.
7. A. TSARBOPOULOS, B. PRAMANIK, T. L. NAGABHUSHAN and T. R. COVEY, *J. Mass Spectrom.*, 1995, **30**, 1752.
8. A. TSARBOPOULOS, M. KARAS, K. STRUPAT, B. N. PRAMANIK, T. L. NAGABHUSHAN and F. HILLENKAMP, *Anal. Chem.*, 1994, **66**, 2062; A. TSARPOULOS, U. BAHR, B. N. PRAMANIK and M. KARAS, *Int. J. Mass Spectrom. Ion Proc.*, 1997, **169/170**, 251.
9. B. GANEM, Y. T. LI and J. D. HENION, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1991, **113**, 6294, 7818; M. BACA and B. KENT, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1992, **114**, 3992; K. J. LIGHT-WAHL, D. L. SPRINGER, B. E. WINGER, C. G. EDMONDS, D. G. CAMP II, B. D. THRALL and R. D. SMITH, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1993, **115**, 803.
10. A. K. GANGULY, B. N. PRAMANIK, A. TSARBOPOULOS, T. R. COVEY, E. C. HUANG and S. A. FUHRMAN, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1992, **114**, 6559.
11. E. C. HUANG, B. N. PRAMANIK, A. TSARBOPOULOS, P. REICHERT, A. K. GANGULY, P. P. TROTTA and T. L. NAGABHUSHAN, *J. Am. Soc. Mass Spectrom.*, 1993, **4**, 624.
12. A. K. GANGULY, B. N. PRAMANIK, E. C. HUANG, A. TSARBOPOULOS, V. M. GIRIJAVALLABHAN and S. LIBERLES, *Tetrahedron*, 1993, **49**, 7985.
13. A. G. TAVERAS, S. REMISZEWSKI, R. J. DOLL, D. CESARZ, J. DEL ROSARIO, B. VIBULBHAN, B. BAUER, J. E. BROWN, D. CARR, J. CATINO, C. A. EVANS, V. GIRIJAVALLABHAN, E. C. HUANG, L. HEIMARK, L. JAMES, P. KIRSCHMEIER, S. LIBERLES, S. NASH, B. N. PRAMANIK, M. M. SENIOR, M. E. SNOW, A. TSARBOPOULOS, Y. -S. WANG, A. K. GANGULY, R. AUST, E. BROWN, D. DELISLE, S. FUHRMAN, T. HENDRICKSON, C. KISSINGER, R. LOVE, W. SISSON, E. VILAFRANCA and S. E. WEBBER, *Bioorg. Med. Chem.*, 1997, **5**, 125.
14. A. K. GANGULY, B. N. PRAMANIK, E. C. HUANG, S. LIBERLES, L. HEIMARK, Y. H. LIU, A. TSARBOPOULOS, R. J. DOLL, A. G. TAVERAS, S. REMISZEWSKI, M. E. SNOW, Y. S. WANG, B. VIBULBHAN, D. CESARZ, J. E. BROWN, J. DEL ROSARIO, L. JAMES, P. KIRSCHMEIER and V. GIRIJAVALLABHAN, *Bioorg. Med. Chem.*, 1997, **5**, 817.